
Website

Deliverable no.

D6.1

Nature, dissemination level

Report, public

Lead beneficiaries

9 – RECC Regional Environmental Centre for the Caucasus

1 – IIWH Internationales Institut für Wald und Holzwirtschaft NRW e.V.

Main authors

Uwe Kies, Sophiko Akhobadze

Approved by

Andreas Schulte (coordinator)

Date, version

30 Sep 2014, 1st submission

REC Caucasus
150, Aghmashenebeli Ave., 7th Floor
0112 Tbilisi, Georgia
fon +995 32 2253649 / 2253648
www.rec-caucasus.org

Internationales Institut für Wald und Holz NRW e.V.
Hafenweg 24a, 48155 Münster, Germany
fon +49 251 674 3240, fax +49 251 674 32421
www.wald-zentrum.de

Table of contents

1.	Purpose	3
2.	Progress	3
2.1	Setup.....	3
2.2	Main frame	4
2.3	Main contents and articles	5
3.	Editing and Updates	6
4.	Annex	7
4.1	Screenshot examples of website articles	7
4.2	Screenshot examples of the CMS.....	16

1. Purpose

The project website www.reram.eu is the main tool to support and enlarge the consortium's dissemination and exploitation activities.

Objectives and description from DoW Annex I (Workplan WP6 p. 19):

The overall objective of WP6 is to promote and to enhance the awareness of R2I-related activities in the field of Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials among the broad range of stakeholder groups involved. (...) Task 6.2, A. Project website: The project website collects coordinated input of all partners to address different target groups of the RERAM results: user groups within the Resource Efficiency/Raw Materials-sector, public authorities on different levels, the scientific community and the wider public. Special care is taken to present the results in a clear way adapted to different audiences, pointing out the overall impact on the sector, as well as environmental, economical and societal implications. The website is widely linked to other relevant sites.

This deliverable D6.1 reports on the progress of the website development, which has been setup in multiple languages to attain a maximum of different target audiences.

2. Progress

2.1 Setup

The website has been located at www.reram.eu. The website has been developed by the editorial team of RECC, FORZA, IIWH and PROKO. The website is owned by the coordinator IIWH. The technical implementation was realised by Connectiv! eSolutions GmbH, Lingen, Germany, www.connectiv.de.

The website uses an efficient **Content Management System (CMS)**, WebCMS 4.5, which allows a fast and secure 'on the fly'-editing. All website components and contents are accessible via the CMS.

The multilingual website includes **1 + 5 full national language versions**, which will be accessible via the following shortlinks:

English:	www.reram.eu	Ukrainian:	www.reram.eu/ua
German:	www.reram.eu/de	Moldovan:	www.reram.eu/md
Polish:	www.reram.eu/pl	Georgian:	www.reram.eu/ge

The website has been set up with a core of content, to be further extended throughout the project. The English version is **online since 22 Sep 2014**. The technical setup of the other five language versions is finished and the preparation/translation of contents is in progress. All language versions are expected to be online until November 2014.

2.2 Main frame

Figure 2.2. Main frame and start page of the project website www.reram.eu

About Partners Regions Outputs Contact

RERAM
research to innovation in
resource efficiency

You are here: [Home](#) / [About](#)

Project in a nutshell

RERAM = Resource Efficiency and Raw Material use of woodworking industries in Eastern Europe (ENP)

State of play
The growing demand for raw wood material in the EU increases pressure on forest resources...

Vision & Objectives
RERAM improves Resource Efficiency and Raw Material consumption of the forest-based sector...

Outcomes & Impacts
RERAM raises awareness on the benefits of resource efficiency and demonstrates technical and...

Consortium
11 organisations represent the 4 EU member states Germany, Austria, Poland, Belgium and the...

Support

The RERAM project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under the grant agreement no. 609573.

The Ministry of Innovation, Science and Research of the Federal State of North Rhine-Westphalia (MIWF NRW) provides a cofunding.

Latest News and Articles

RERAM Videoclip
Resource efficiency is a major opportunity to improve raw material use and clean production in wood industries of Eastern Europe. This short video introduces RERAM's main objectives and the project partners.

Upcoming: Trainers' Week in Lviv, Ukraine, 13-18 Oct 2014
A trainers' programme in resource and energy efficiency management for wood-based industries will be held in the beautiful city of Lviv, Western Ukraine, hosted by the Ukrainian National Forestry University (UNFU) and FORZA NGO. The training programme...

RERAM Kickoff Meeting in Münster, Germany, 14-17 July 2014
Preserving wood resources in Europe - Wald-Zentrum Münster initiates a second EU project in forestry and wood industries. 25 experts started successfully their work on the 2-years project.

Regions: ENP Eastern Partnership countries
RERAM reaches out to Eastern Partnership countries of the European Neighbourhood Policy programme (ENP EAP). Building on experience from wood cluster regions in Germany (NRW), Austria (Styria) and Poland (Wielkopolska), the project targets complementary...

Wald-Zentrum IiWH International Institute of Forestry and Wood Industries NRW e.V. (Coordinator)
The Wald-Zentrum / IiWH is a German competence centre in forestry, wood-based industries and international cooperation. It was founded in 2003 by the State Government of NRW and the University of Münster to respond to the both ecological and economical...

News & Upcoming events

Upcoming: Trainers' Week in Lviv, Ukraine, 13-18 Oct 2014
A trainers' programme in resource and energy efficiency management for wood-based industries will be held...

Upcoming: 9th ILN workshop, Brussels, 27-28 Nov 2014
The International Learning Network (ILN) workshop "International cooperation in Horizon 2020" will be held...

Upcoming: ener2i Brokerage Event in Moldova, 11 Dec 2014
REAM's partner project ener2i organizes a brokerage event in the framework of the Top Innovation Event, organised...

Past events

RERAM Kickoff Meeting in Münster, Germany, 14-17 July 2014
Preserving wood resources in Europe - Wald-Zentrum Münster initiates a second EU project in forestry...

EU-EaP STI conference, Yerevan, Armenia, 15-16 May 2014
RERAM was represented in the EU-EaP STI policy stakeholders conference hosted by the National Academy of...

8th ILN workshop in Budapest, Nov 6-8, 2013
The first R2I Cluster meeting of the 13 new INCO projects took place during the 8th ILN workshop held in...

Sitemap Legal notice Terms and Conditions

The main frame includes: i) the visual header with the project logo and an image teaser, ii) the main menu at the top, iii) the left-side bar with interactive sub menus, iv) the right-side bar listing news, upcoming and past events, v) the text box acknowledging the EC FP7 financial support, and vi) the footer including the sitemap, legal notice and the terms and conditions.

2.3 Main contents and articles

<i>Menu, article</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Short link</i>
Start page	Latest news and articles	www.reram.eu
About		
Key facts	General overview and key infos on the project	www.reram.eu/about/factsheet.html
Videoclip	5-min videoclip introducing the project and statements of partners	www.reram.eu/about/video.html
State of play	Why a focus on the woodworking sector in ENP countries?	www.reram.eu/about/stateofplay.html
Vision & Objectives		www.reram.eu/about/objectives.html
Outcomes & Impacts	Main outcomes per target group	www.reram.eu/about/outcomes.html
Work Packages	WPs and WP Leaders	www.reram.eu/about/wp.html
Partners		
Consortium	Presentation of all 11 consortium member organisations with an individual page including a short profile and contact info	www.reram.eu/partners/consortium.html
Woodworking SMEs	Purpose of the 'ground truth check' of the main target group is explained. Section to be further elaborated later.	www.reram.eu/partners/sme.html
Associated partners	Role of associated partners. Section to be further elaborated later.	www.reram.eu/partners/associated.html
R2I Cluster	List of partner projects of the FP7-INCO project cluster	www.reram.eu/partners/r2icluster.html
Regions		
ENP EaP countries	Rationale of complementarities among ENP target regions and EU benchmarking regions	www.reram.eu/regions/enp-eap.html
Carpathia, UA	Carpathia profile	www.reram.eu/regions/ua.html
Moldova	Moldova profile	www.reram.eu/regions/md.html
Georgia	Georgia profile	www.reram.eu/regions/ge.html
Armenia	Armenia profile	www.reram.eu/regions/ar.html
Azerbaijan	Azerbaijan profile	www.reram.eu/regions/az.html
NRW, Germany	NRW profile	www.reram.eu/regions/de.html
Styria, Austria	Styria profile	www.reram.eu/regions/at.html
Wielkopolska, PL	Wielkopolska profile	www.reram.eu/regions/pl.html

Outputs		
Publications	List of downloadable multilingual publications: dissemination kit, video/audio, reports, presentations. Regularly appended and updated.	www.reram.eu/outputs/publications.html
Events	List of RERAM meetings and related events with participation of consortium members. Individual subpages per event. Regularly appended and updated.	www.reram.eu/outputs/events/events.html
Press review	List of partners' press releases and review of project-related press articles. Regularly appended and updated.	www.reram.eu/outputs/press.html
Photo gallery	Selection of photos from project meetings and events	www.reram.eu/outputs/photos.html
Contact	Contact info of coordinator and consortium members	www.reram.eu/contact/contact.html
Footer		
Sitemap	Table of website structure	www.reram.eu/about/sitemap.html
Legal notice	Owner of website, copyright statement, acknowledgement of FP7 funding	www.reram.eu/about/legal-notice.html
Terms and Conditions	Copyright notice, disclaimer, personal data protection, Google Analytics	www.reram.eu/about/terms.html

3. Editing and Updates

The WP6 **editorial team** (IIWH, PROKO, RECC, FORZA) is responsible for managing and editing the website during the project. The WP6 Leaders RECC and FORZA coordinate the joint dissemination activities and ensure the timely collection of inputs from partners to update the website contents in regular intervals (cf. D6.2 Dissemination Strategy). Further team members of the consortium are assigned as **national editors** with access to the CMS, who are responsible for editing and proofreading the language versions. The **Project Assistant PROKO** is responsible for ensuring the technical realisation of the editing/updates and offers technical guidance/support on the CMS to the website editors. The website will document and publish all relevant results and outcomes of the project and stay online for at least 3 years after the end of project.

4. Annex

4.1 Screenshot examples of website articles

Figure 4.1.1 Introduction page, example 'State of Play'

Project in a nutshell

RERAM = Resource Efficiency and Raw Material use of woodworking industries in Eastern Europe (ENP)

Vision & Objectives
RERAM improves Resource Efficiency and Raw Material consumption of the forest-based sector...

Outcomes & Impacts
RERAM raises awareness on the benefits of resource efficiency and demonstrates technical and...

Consortium
11 organisations represent the 4 EU member states Germany, Austria, Poland, Belgium and the...

State of play

Why a focus on the woodworking sector in ENP eastern countries?

The growing demand for raw wood material in the EU increases pressure on forest resources in Eastern Europe. Non-sustainable forestry and uncontrolled timber harvesting in the Carpathian region (Ukraine, Moldova) and the Caucasus region (Georgia, Armenia, Azerbadjan) lead to significant losses of forest area and far-reaching impacts e.g. disastrous floods.

The European 'wood gap' pushes raw material exports from forests in ENP countries holding considerable, less developed forest resources with a lower land use pressure than in the EU. The ENP region is an emerging strategic market for raw material supply with many downsides, e.g. illegal logging and timber trade, offshoring of production, cut-throat competition, corruption.

1/3

Figure. Forest cover losses, clearcuts, outdated sawmill equipment and wood wastes in Western Ukraine.

Woodworking industries generate the local demand for wood and are part of the problem due to their large, inefficient raw material use. Woodworking SMEs consuming huge amounts of raw material, per employee, and in total. These industries currently emerge anew in post-socialist countries and could have a stronger impact on regional production, employment and value added.

However, SMEs mostly lack proper structures and staff to implement even basic, urgently needed resource efficiency measures. Applicable knowhow and technologies of a sustainable material use and resource supply are largely unknown or not accessible so far. Useable guidance required for the shift is so far lacking, because existing toolkits are too complicated for the outdated equipment still in use in ENP countries.

> **Vision & Objectives**

Support

The RERAM project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under the grant agreement no. 609573.

The Ministry of Innovation, Science and Research of the Federal State of North Rhine-Westphalia (MIWF NRW) provides a cofunding.

Figure 4.1.2 Overview page, example 'Consortium'

Partners

Woodworking SMEs
RERAM targets gaps in the R2I knowledge chain from a strong enterprise level perspective....

Associated partners
RERAM reaches out to R2I actors and key players in the ENP Eastern Partnership region...

R2I Research to Innovation Cluster
RERAM belongs to a cluster of EU funded FP7-INCO projects supporting the link between...

IIWH International Institute of Forestry and Wood Industries NRW e.V. (Coordinator)
The Wald-Zentrum / IIWH is a German competence centre in forestry, wood-based industries...

Support

The RERAM project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under the grant agreement no. 609573.

The Ministry of Innovation, Science and Research of the Federal State of North Rhine-Westphalia (MIWF NRW) provides a cofunding.

Consortium

11 organisations represent the 4 EU member states Germany, Austria, Poland, Belgium and the 5 ENP Eastern countries Ukraine, Moldova, Georgia, Armenia and Azerbaijan. The RERAM core group of organisations builds on a long partnership from previous collaborations and reaches out to neighbouring ENP countries to extend their partnership with further compatible regions and strong R2I players in the forest-based sector.

> **Please click** on the Logo to find the profile, contacts and further info of the organisations. An overview list of the project team members you can find under > **Contact**.

 ITD Instytut Technologii Drewna (Wood Technology Institute) Poznan, Poland		
 WPFC Wood Processing and Furniture Cluster Lviv, Ukraine		
 AUG Agricultural University of Georgia Tbilisi, Georgia		
 PROKO PROJEKTkompetenz.eu Salzburg, Austria		

Figure 4.1.3 Partner page, example 'FORZA NGO'

Partners

Consortium
11 organisations represent the 4 EU member states Germany, Austria, Poland, Belgium and...

Woodworking SMEs
RERAM targets gaps in the R2I knowledge chain from a strong enterprise level perspective....

Associated partners
RERAM reaches out to R2I actors and key players in the ENP Eastern Partnership region...

R2I Research to Innovation Cluster
RERAM belongs to a cluster of EU funded FP7-INCO projects supporting the link between...

IIWH International Institute of Forestry and Wood Industries NRW e.V. (Coordinator)
The Wald-Zentrum / IIWH is a German competence centre in forestry, wood-based industries...

FORZA NGO - Agency for Sustainable Development of the Carpathian Region

NGO FORZA is a non-profit non-governmental organization led by the main goal of promotion of sustainable development of the Carpathian region of Ukraine in the economic, environmental and social aspects of natural resource management and community development. Since its initiation, FORZA is build upon a close network to governmental bodies and the private sector, among others the State Forest Resource Agency, the regional forest administrations, local enterprises and NGOs.

Main competences

- ✦ Expert and technical support to communities and regional SME's in various fields, such as sustainable, multifunctional, participatory forest management, cluster analysis, capacity building of local actors, facilitation of marketing of wooden products, networking and partnership, stakeholder analysis, sustainable tourism development, community development planning, climate change adaptation, energy efficiency
- ✦ Organization and facilitation of workshops, conferences, forums, project design / management
- ✦ Development and organization of capacity building and professional training programs/events

Contact

Mrs. Lesya Loyko
+380312 671450
NGO head, project manager
lesya.loyko@forza.org.ua

Mrs. Natalya Voloshyna
project expert
natalya.voloshyn@forza.org.ua

Mrs. Radmila Ustych
project expert
radmila.ustych@forza.org.ua

FORZA NGO
Mynajska str. 27/39
88018 Uzhgorod, Ukraine
www.forza.org.ua

➤ **FORZA presentation**

- Leader of **WP6 - Dissemination**
- ENP target region: **Western Ukraine / Carpathian Region**
- ◀ **Consortium**

Support

The RERAM project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under the grant agreement no. 609573.

The Ministry of Innovation, Science and Research of the Federal State of North Rhine-Westphalia (MIWF NRW) provides a cofunding.

Figure 4.1.4 Overview page, example 'R2I Research to Innovation Cluster'

Partners

Consortium
11 organisations represent the 4 EU member states Germany, Austria, Poland, Belgium and...

Woodworking SMEs
RERAM targets gaps in the R2I knowledge chain from a strong enterprise level perspective....

Associated partners
RERAM reaches out to R2I actors and key players in the ENP Eastern Partnership region....

IIVH International Institute of Forestry and Wood Industries NRW e.V. (Coordinator)
The Wald-Zentrum / IIVH is a German competence centre in forestry, wood-based industries...

Support

The RERAM project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under the grant agreement no. 609573.

The Ministry of Innovation, Science and Research of the Federal State of North Rhine-Westphalia (MIWF NRW) provides a cofunding.

R2I Research to Innovation Cluster

RERAM belongs to a cluster of EU funded FP7-INCO projects supporting the link between research and innovation in the Eastern Partnership (EaP) and in the Mediterranean countries. The R2I EaP cluster builds on regular exchange and joint coordinated activities of the projects.

EaP Cluster

 IncoNet <i>Eastern Partnership</i> <i>STI International Cooperation Network for Eastern Partnership Countries</i> CeRISS Athens, Greece inco-eap.net		
 innover EAST <i>Bridging the gap in R2I between EU and the EPCs in energy efficiency</i> Bay Zoltan Nonprofit Ltd. Budapest, Hungary innovereast.eu		

Med Cluster

 MARE <i>Mediterranean Activities for Research and Innovation in the Energy sector</i> CRES Athens, Greece mare-euromed.eu		
 Healthy <i>Mediterranean Research Network on Footcare Sector</i> CMTCC Casablanca, Maroc sohealthyproject.eu		

Figure 4.1.5 Overview page, example 'Regions'

Figure 4.1.6 Target region info page, example 'Georgia'

Regions

ENP target regions

- Carpathian Region, Ukraine
- Armenia
- Moldova
- Azerbaijan

EU benchmark regions

- Styria, Austria
- North Rhine-Westphalia, Germany
- Wielkopolska, Poland

Georgia

Georgia earth map (Source: Google - [click to enlarge](#))

Georgia (Georgian: Sakartvelo) is a country in the Caucasus region, bounded to by the Black Sea, Russia, Turkey, Armenia, and Azerbaijan. It is a very mountainous country, with the Greater Caucasus Mountain Range forming the northern border. The country covers a territory of 69,700 km², being home to a population of almost 5 million. The capital Tbilisi is the largest city having a population of 1.3 million.

Georgia's forests cover around 2.7 million ha or 40% of the territory with an estimated total growing stock of 434 million m³. The forests however are threatened today: forest management and forest policy enforcement is weak, and illegal timber harvesting is extremely high (World Bank estimates: 2 million m³ per year). Forests are exploited mainly because of the high demand for fuelwood from forests. Cheap fuelwood plays an essential role in Georgia (approx. 15% of the national energy consumption) and is increasing. Furthermore, tending and protection of forests has been neglected for more than a decade now, which is why the forest growth productivity is very low and also forest fires are increasing.

Because of its high diversity in topography, climate and landscapes, Georgia is one of the world's biodiversity hotspots, with a rich variety of unique forest ecosystems. International efforts are under way to designate a major share as protected forest. However scenarios for future timber demand and supply in Georgia prognose a continued overexploitation and an emerging huge deficit of wood resources. Local wood industries and wood products import-export have already largely declined. Intelligent, alternative approaches of sustainable resource use are critical and urgently needed.

Sources: AUG, FAO, ENPI-FLEG

RERAM partners:

- **RECC - Regional Environmental Centre for the Caucasus**
- **AUG - Agricultural University of Georgia**

Figure 4.1.7 Event announcement page, example 'Trainers' Week Lviv'

Project in a nutshell

RERAM = Resource Efficiency and Raw Material use of woodworking industries in Eastern Europe (ENP)

State of play
The growing demand for raw wood material in the EU increases pressure on forest resources...

Vision & Objectives
RERAM improves Resource Efficiency and Raw Material consumption of the forest-based sector...

Outcomes & Impacts
RERAM raises awareness on the benefits of resource efficiency and demonstrates technical and...

Consortium
11 organisations represent the 4 EU member states Germany, Austria, Poland, Belgium and the...

Upcoming: Trainers' Week in Lviv, Ukraine, 13-18 Oct 2014

A trainers' programme in resource and energy efficiency management for wood-based industries will be held in the beautiful city of Lviv, Western Ukraine, hosted by the Ukrainian National Forestry University (UNFU) and FORZA NGO. The training programme will be provided by the Austrian Wood Cluster Styria (HCS) in collaboration with two specialists.

The training modules comprise theoretical introductions and interactive exercises on:

- Cleaner Production and Resource Efficiency
- Material flow analysis
- Water Management and Waste Management
- Tools and Efficiency Guidelines

The practical training will include excursions to the woodworking enterprises in the Lviv region:

- **FAKRO-Lviv** - window manufacturer
- **BUK-HOLDING** - producer of windows, doors, stairs and staircases, balusters, barriers, other small wooden items for interior design
- **YURVIT** - producer of furniture from solid wood
- **Joiners and carpenters professional school** in Yaniv

A full "real check day" together with the trainers will be performed on the example of the enterprise **"FURNITURE STYLE"**. Visiting the production units the trainers will try to identify the possible ways of the resource and energy efficiency meet with the enterprise management and discuss the observations and improvement options.

➤ **Press information** (in Ukrainian)

Contacts for further info:

FORZA - Lesya Loyko
UNFU - Prof. Orest Kiyko
HCS - Roland Oberwimmer

➤ **Events**

Support

The RERAM project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under the grant agreement no. 609573.

The Ministry of Innovation, Science and Research of the Federal State of North Rhine-Westphalia (MIWF NRW) provides a cofunding.

Figure 4.1.8 Download page, example ‘Publications’

Outputs

[Press review](#)

[Photo gallery](#)

[Events](#)

Publications

[Dissemination kit](#)

*Downloads and websites:
> left click to open in new window,
or right click to download file !*

Project factsheet (2 pages)

Project summary profile (5 pages)

Project presentation - PDF (10 slides)

Project presentation - Powerpoint (10 slides)

Complete Dissemination Kit - ZIP

EN | DE | PL | UA | MD | GE | RU

EN | DE | PL | UA | MD | GE | RU

EN | DE | PL | UA | MD | GE | RU

EN | DE | PL | UA | MD | GE | RU

ALL.zip

Video + Audio

RERAM Videoclip - Introduction

RERAM Podcast - German radio feature at Deutschlandfunk

EN | DE download: **EN | DE**

DE download: **DE**

Reports

[Guidelines for woodworking SMEs \(draft version\)](#)

Presentations

[Presentation X at conference Y](#)

Support

The RERAM project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under the grant agreement no. 609573.

The Ministry of Innovation, Science and Research of the Federal State of North Rhine-Westphalia (MIWF NRW) provides a cofunding.

Figure 4.1.9 Download page, example 'Press review'

Outputs

Publications

Photo gallery

Events

Support

The RERAM project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under the grant agreement no. 609573.

The Ministry of Innovation, Science and Research of the Federal State of North Rhine-Westphalia (MIWF NRW) provides a cofunding.

Press review

List of partners' press releases and project-related press features.
 ▶ *Top articles are marked with the arrow.*

Date	Medium	Nature	Links / Downloads
13/10/2014	UNFU / FORZA press release	press release	UA
27/09/2014	UNFU website	info	UA EN
16/07/2014	WPFC website	info	UA EN
14/09/2014	▶ Georgian TV station "Agency PIA"	TV interview	GE Youtube
14/09/2014	AUG press release	press release	GE EN
25/07/2014	Westfalium Pressemitteilung	press release	DE pdf
18/07/2014	ARD-Mediathek	online radio	DE
16/07/2014	Westfälische-Nachrichten	print article	DE
16/07/2014	WWU Pressemitteilung upm	press release	DE
15/07/2014	Windkraft-Journal	press release	DE pdf
15/07/2014	WDR2 radio	radio feature	DE
14/07/2014	Münstersche Zeitung	print article	DE pdf
15/07/2014	▶ Deutschlandfunk.de	radio podcast	DE pdf mp3
15/07/2014	Mittelstand-Nachrichten	press release	DE pdf
14/07/2014	IWH website	press release	DE pdf
14/07/2014	▶ RERAM website	press release	EN
12/09/2014	ITD press release	press release	PL
16/07/2014	ITD website	info	PL EN

4.2 Screenshot examples of the CMS

Figure 4.2.1 CMS, example website folder architecture

Datum: 27.09.2014
Redakteur: kies

 WebSite direkt bearbeiten
(Direct-Edit Modus)

abmelden
connectiv!
WebCMS 4.5

Inhalte bearbeiten
Redakteure

[Kategorien/Artikel](#) | [Medien verwalten](#) | [Metatags](#) | [Übersetzungstabelle](#) | [Gelöschte Artikel](#)

Inhalte bearbeiten > Kategorien/Artikel

Alle Artikel anzeigen
Unsichtbare Artikel anzeigen
?

Navigation ⌵

Hauptnavigation	NEUE KATEGORIE
<input type="checkbox"/> (172) main	<input type="checkbox"/> NEUE KATEGORIE KATEGORIE UMHÄNGEN KATEGORIE LÖSCHEN
<input type="checkbox"/> (74) About	<input type="checkbox"/> NEUE KATEGORIE KATEGORIE UMHÄNGEN KATEGORIE LÖSCHEN
<input type="checkbox"/> (128) Key facts (Weiterleitung auf Artikel)	<input type="checkbox"/> NEUE KATEGORIE KATEGORIE UMHÄNGEN KATEGORIE LÖSCHEN
<input type="checkbox"/> (173) Videoclip (Weiterleitung auf Artikel)	<input type="checkbox"/> NEUE KATEGORIE KATEGORIE UMHÄNGEN KATEGORIE LÖSCHEN
<input type="checkbox"/> (133) State of Play (Weiterleitung auf Artikel)	<input type="checkbox"/> NEUE KATEGORIE KATEGORIE UMHÄNGEN KATEGORIE LÖSCHEN
<input type="checkbox"/> (129) Vision & Objectives (Weiterleitung auf Artikel)	<input type="checkbox"/> NEUE KATEGORIE KATEGORIE UMHÄNGEN KATEGORIE LÖSCHEN
<input type="checkbox"/> (131) Outcomes & Impacts (Weiterleitung auf Artikel)	<input type="checkbox"/> NEUE KATEGORIE KATEGORIE UMHÄNGEN KATEGORIE LÖSCHEN
<input type="checkbox"/> (165) Work Packages (Weiterleitung auf Artikel)	<input type="checkbox"/> NEUE KATEGORIE KATEGORIE UMHÄNGEN KATEGORIE LÖSCHEN
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (75) Partners	<input type="checkbox"/> NEUE KATEGORIE KATEGORIE UMHÄNGEN KATEGORIE LÖSCHEN
<input type="checkbox"/> (81) Consortium	<input type="checkbox"/> NEUE KATEGORIE KATEGORIE UMHÄNGEN KATEGORIE LÖSCHEN
<input type="checkbox"/> (171) Coordinator IIWH (Weiterleitung auf Artikel)	<input type="checkbox"/> NEUE KATEGORIE KATEGORIE UMHÄNGEN KATEGORIE LÖSCHEN
<input type="checkbox"/> (168) Woodworking SMEs (Weiterleitung auf Artikel)	<input type="checkbox"/> NEUE KATEGORIE KATEGORIE UMHÄNGEN KATEGORIE LÖSCHEN
<input type="checkbox"/> (162) Associated partners (Weiterleitung auf Artikel)	<input type="checkbox"/> NEUE KATEGORIE KATEGORIE UMHÄNGEN KATEGORIE LÖSCHEN
<input type="checkbox"/> (163) R2I Cluster (Weiterleitung auf Artikel)	<input type="checkbox"/> NEUE KATEGORIE KATEGORIE UMHÄNGEN KATEGORIE LÖSCHEN
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (134) Regions	<input type="checkbox"/> NEUE KATEGORIE KATEGORIE UMHÄNGEN KATEGORIE LÖSCHEN
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (76) News & Events	<input type="checkbox"/> NEUE KATEGORIE KATEGORIE UMHÄNGEN KATEGORIE LÖSCHEN
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (110) Outputs	<input type="checkbox"/> NEUE KATEGORIE KATEGORIE UMHÄNGEN KATEGORIE LÖSCHEN
<input type="checkbox"/> (77) Contact	<input type="checkbox"/> NEUE KATEGORIE KATEGORIE UMHÄNGEN KATEGORIE LÖSCHEN
<input type="checkbox"/> Linke Navigation	<input type="checkbox"/> NEUE KATEGORIE
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Footer Navigation	<input type="checkbox"/> NEUE KATEGORIE

Alle Strukturpunkte öffnen / Alle Strukturpunkte schließen

Bei Fragen zum CM-System wenden Sie sich jederzeit gerne an service@connectiv.de oder an den telefonischen Support unter: 0591-80032-0
Komprimierung: gzip

Figure 4.2.2 CMS, example media management folder

Datum: 27.09.2014
Redakteur: kies

 WebSite direkt bearbeiten
(Direct-Edit Modus)

 abmelden

connectiv!
WebCMS 4.5

Inhalte bearbeiten | Redakteure

Kategorien/Artikel | [Medien verwalten](#) | [Metatags](#) | [Übersetzungstabelle](#) | [Gelöschte Artikel](#)

Inhalte bearbeiten > Medien verwalten > Ordner: "maps"

?

Ordnerstruktur

Bilder allgemein		
0-symbols (6 Dateien)		X
2014-07-14_kickoff (25 Dateien)		X
2014-10-13_lviv (5 Dateien)		X
dissemination (2 Dateien)		X
flags (10 Dateien)		X
header (8 Dateien)		X
logos (20 Dateien)		X
logos2 (17 Dateien)		X
maps (9 Dateien)		X
people (17 Dateien)		X
photos_enp_fbs (8 Dateien)		X
premises (6 Dateien)		X
teaser (17 Dateien)		X

PDF-Dateien		
dissemination_kit (3 Dateien)		X
partner_infos (6 Dateien)		X
press_de (13 Dateien)		X
press_en (0 Dateien)		X
press_pl (1 Datei)		X
press_ua (1 Datei)		X

Sonstige Dateien		
audio (1 Datei)		X
videos (0 Dateien)		X

Word-Dateien		
		X

Excel Dateien		
		X

Powerpoint-Dateien		
		X

Geschützte Dateien		
		X

Im Ordner "maps" befindliche Dateien:

armenia_google_L... Größe: 301,17 KB Max.Maß: 637 x 633	azerbaijan_googl... Größe: 598,86 KB Max.Maß: 1101 x 900	georgia_google_L... Größe: 616,36 KB Max.Maß: 1351 x 730	moldova_physical... Größe: 750,39 KB Max.Maß: 1416 x 1803	nrw... Größe: ... Max.Maß: ...

Neue Dateien auf den Server übertragen:

DATEIEN AUSWÄHLEN
 ALLE DATEIEN ENTFERNEN

Gesamtfortschritt (0 B) 0%

Datei Fortschritt 0%

Dateien hochladen

Bilder beim Hochladen nicht skalieren:

Einstellungen des Bildordners:

Hinweis: Bereits hochgeladene Bilder werden bei Änderung der Maße nicht angepasst!

Normal:	Breite: <input type="text" value="350"/>	Höhe: <input type="text" value="0"/> Pixel
Vergrößert:	Breite: <input type="text" value="1500"/>	Höhe: <input type="text" value="0"/> Pixel
Verkleinert:	Breite: <input type="text" value="144"/>	Höhe: <input type="text" value="0"/> Pixel
Sondermaß 1:	Breite: <input type="text" value="610"/>	Höhe: <input type="text" value="0"/> Pixel
Sondermaß 2:	Breite: <input type="text" value="225"/>	Höhe: <input type="text" value="130"/> Pixel

Änderungen speichern

Hinweis: Jedes Bild wird in verschiedenen Größen auf dem Server gespeichert. Diese unterschiedlich großen Bilder können dann in verschiedenen Bausteinen zum Einsatz kommen. Ein Beispiel hierfür wäre der "Aktuelles - Artikel" - Baustein, in dem ein Bild klein in der Übersicht erscheint, aber groß im Artikel selbst.
 Die gewünschten Größen können Sie oben einstellen. Lautet das festgelegte Bildmaß einer Kopie 0 x 0 Pixel, dann wird keine Kopie angelegt. Dies gilt nicht für die Hauptbildgröße. Steht diese auf 0 x 0 Pixel, so wird das Bild in der Originalgröße hochgeladen.

Bei Fragen zum CM-System wenden Sie sich jederzeit gerne an service@connectiv.de oder an den telefonischen Support unter: 0591-80032-0

Komprimierung: gzip

